

LOW VELOCITY IMPACT DAMAGE OF ORGANIC FOAM CORE SANDWICH COMPOSITES

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SUMMARY: The purpose of this study was to determine the amount of damage resulting in a sandwich shell composite due to impact by a mass with different impact energies. In addition, information on the failure characteristics versus the energy of the impact was desired. While there has been substantial work on impact damage of a number of laminated composites, little work exists on sandwich composites. The authors intended to investigate low velocity impact of sandwich panels using a drop weight system. The dynamic response of sandwich shells to low velocity impact is complex, and our ability to detect threshold damage is important, and the influence of core density on impact dynamics has not been investigated. We just concluded tests on 23 sandwich panels of three core densities at the Wright Patterson Flight Dynamics Laboratory Dynatup drop weight facility. Impact energies ranged from 0.28 to 36.9 Newton Meters.

While the number of samples is low, we have been able to determine the threshold energy producing incipient front-face damage as well as the energy producing maximum impact force after which catastrophic front face failure results. In addition, we have compared our results with those of laminated composite panels with a comparable number of plies. Sandwich panels are surprisingly robust, particularly resisting lower energy damage, and the density of the core has minimal affect on the panel stiffness. However, core density has a dramatic affect on the contact forces at impact. In addition, peak forces during impact are equivalent to peak forces achieved in quasi-static tests indicating that the inertia of a sandwich system is of no significant influence.

KEYWORDS: low velocity impact, sandwich plates, damage, damage tolerance

INTRODUCTION

Low velocity impact is important in sandwich shell composites for a number of reasons. Perhaps most importantly, low-velocity impact can lead to damage which is frequently not detected by visual means. Secondly, it can lead to damage which substantially reduces the ability of the structure to survive the loads it was designed to resist. Since modern aircraft and aerospace vehicles are designed to minimize added weight, there is less margin of safety than with fixed structures making an accurate knowledge of failure more important.

Since composite materials are typically strong and stiff, they are prime candidates for aircraft structures, and since many applications are stiffness rather than strength driven, sandwich shell composites are ideal candidates for efficient aerospace structures. Some properties shared by many fiber-reinforced composites laminates include a low ultimate strain and

strength through the thickness [1]. Sandwich shell composite core materials also have a low shear and compression strength in comparison to the face sheets. By comparison to laminates, sandwich shell structures exhibit excellent stiffness and strength in bending and a low specific weight.

While this sounds like an ideal structural material for aeronautical and aerospace applications, impact resistance restricts the use of such structures where public safety is an issue. Low velocity impact testing, where velocities are under 12.2 m/s, is particularly important because 1) it can weaken the material without producing visible damage, 2) there are so many phenomena including improper manufacturing and assembly of sandwich shell components which can lead to this damage, and 3) the need to create more cost-effective, stiff, light-weight structures is forcing the industry to reconsider sandwich shells. Other factors limiting the usefulness of such materials include their tendency to absorb moisture. In fact foam cores made of polymethacrylimide (PMI) absorb high amounts of water as compared to honeycomb cores [2]. The objectives of the research were to investigate the low velocity impact damage at different energies, to determine the characteristics three different core densities contribute to the impact resistance of sandwich composites, and to compare the nature of damage inflicted by static and dynamic events.

PREPARATION OF PANELS

Only sandwich plates formed into layered flat plates of dimension 178 mm by 254 mm are used for this study. The thickness of the plates is standardized at 19 mm although a planned extended study will include other core thicknesses. The external (face) sheets are made of nine laminae made of single plain weave carbon graphite fibers with an epoxy resin (Diaminodiphenyl Sulfone). This produces a final sheet of from 1.65 to 1.73 mm in thickness. The resulting plane weave laminate is similar to the [0/90] orientation in unidirectional laminates. The [0/90] stacking sequence is a common one which parallels that of the Cristescu [3] study. The McQuillen & Gause study, where a stacking sequence of $[\pm 45/0_2/\pm 45]_s$ was used, gave very similar results for low velocity impact damage [4].

The external sheets of graphite epoxy laminates were fabricated and tested in the Center for Composite Materials Research (CCMR) within the Department of Mechanical Engineering at North Carolina A&T State University. The outer and inner face sheets were laminated in a hydraulic press. The Hydraulic Press was initially heated to 121°C and allowed to reach a pressure 689.5 kPa and temperature of 177°C. throughout all layers of

The coefficient of expansion for the resin and fibers are substantially different, and they can cause parasitic internal stresses unless processing is done carefully and consistently. After the laminate has been maintained at the prescribed temperature and pressure, the laminate was allowed to cool at 2 degrees per minute. This rate allows enough time for an annealing action reducing the parasitic stresses due to the thermal expansion mismatch. Material Property tests were conducted on the face sheets via an MTS-810 machine; the in-plane properties along the fiber directions are: 68.2 GPa (tensile modulus), 633 MPa (tensile strength), and 412 MPa (compressive strength). The external sheets strength properties were taken from a nine ply laminate specimens cut from sheets originally of dimension 0.42 Meter by 0.51 Meter. The tensile tests followed the American Standard for Test and Materials (ASTM) D 638-94b. Compression tests followed ASTM D 1621-94.

Rohacell is a polymethacrylimide (PMI) foam. The core material for our sandwich panels was fabricated from one layer of Rohacell. The construction was chosen to approximate an efficient structure maintaining both high stiffness and strength, in resisting bending loads. Rohacell foam can be acquired in a variety of densities and shear and compressive strengths. One important consideration in using it for this work is that we could experiment with combinations of core properties to obtain an optimized structure.

The Rohacell core is easily machinable and the cost is less than standard honeycomb (Nomex); however, it is hygroscopic and it has both a low shear strength and stiffness. Mass densities of 32, 52, and 75 Kg/M³ have been selected for the core since they represent a range of properties of sandwich cores, and the effect of core density on impact damage is an important part of the study. They are referred to as R-31, R-51, and R-71. The Table below indicates some important stiffness and strength parameters for Rohacell.

Table 1: Rohacell stiffness and strength properties

Density (Kg/M ³)	Young's Modulus (N/mm ²)	Shear Modulus (N/mm ²)	Tensile Strength N/mm ²	Compressive Strength N/mm ²	Shear Strength N/mm ²	Flexural Strength N/mm ²
32	36	13	1.0	0.4	0.4	0.8
52	70	19	1.9	0.9	0.8	1.6
75	92	29	2.8	1.5	1.3	2.5

Once the face sheet is formed, the internal sheet is bonded to each of the external sheet in an oven with AF-163 film adhesive. A prescribed heating and cooling rate as part of the curing process helps to control parasitic stresses. Once the sandwich shell laminated composites structures are assembled, they are checked for warping and dimension. They are edge cut to their final shape required for low velocity impact tests, measured for dimensional tolerances, and weighed.

There was concern that conventional cutting equipment could cause delamination at the face-core interfaces, and an Ingersoll-Rand HS-3000 water jet system was used to final cut all specimens. The closed cell geometry is destroyed near machining cuts, and since a water jet was used, each specimen absorbed some water and had to be dried. To do this, specimens were placed into an autoclave for 6 hours at 71.1°C. After cooling, Dow Corning RTV # 737 100% silicone rubber was applied to specimens for water proofing and left intact there through C-SCAN evaluations.

All impact studies were performed at the Wright-Patterson Flight Dynamic Laboratory Dynatup machine drop weight system. In our configuration, the system employs a free-falling drop weight and precision recording system. The drop weight mass was 3.37 Kilograms, and contact with the specimen was made through a 12.7 mm radius indentor normal to the specimen centers. The Boeing test fixture simulating simple support was used. The fixture is important since it controls fixity; fixity affects specimen compliance which changes the force-time impact curve.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

All impact specimens were identical except for the density of the Rohacell foam core. The specimens of Table 2. are sorted by density and drop height. A total of twenty-three specimens were tested in the Dynatup machine. For completeness, specimen ID, impact velocity (m/s), maximum contact force (Newtons), and impact duration (msec.) are displayed. The drop height was measured using a precision gage block set. The quantities including impact velocity, impact force, and impact event duration were all determined experimentally through drop-weight accelerometers which had an output sampling rate of 40 samples per millisecond. All other data in this study can be derived from these values.

Table 2: Tested impact specimens sorted by core density and drop weight height

Specimen ID	Drop Height mm	Density designation	Impact vel. (m/s)	Contact force (N)	Impact duration (msec.)
1	25.40	R-31	0.7071	1458.90	10.97
2	39.42	R-31	0.8778	1569.30	11.65
3	51.77	R-31	0.9997	1721.40	12.15
4	75.74	R-31	1.2009	1887.70	12.90
5	101.60	R-31	1.3929	2176.90	12.57
6	127.00	R-31	1.5575	2264.00	13.25
7	139.70	R-31	1.6368	2303.60	13.43
8	25.67	R-51	0.7102	1672.90	9.05
9	39.22	R-51	0.8717	1949.10	9.70
10	51.36	R-51	0.9967	2216.00	9.88
11	75.77	R-51	1.2009	2393.50	10.55
12	101.50	R-51	1.3929	2471.80	11.23
13	127.00	R-51	1.5575	2698.20	10.95
14	139.70	R-51	1.6368	2537.60	11.75
15	25.40	R-71	0.6706	1790.30	8.02
16	38.86	R-71	0.8656	2162.20	7.93
17	51.13	R-71	0.9967	2471.30	8.43
18	75.44	R-71	1.1979	2985.10	8.25
19	101.20	R-71	1.3868	2852.90	9.72
20	101.60	R-71	1.3929	2890.30	9.40
21	127.00	R-71	1.5606	3253.70	8.85
22	127.00	R-71	1.5636	2944.60	9.60
23	138.90	R-71	1.6368	3047.30	9.92

Before dynamic tests were conducted, a static test was conducted on a sample of each density. Static tests were run on a universal testing machine with the same indenter and Boeing fixture which would be used in all drop weight impact tests. All static tests was conducted at

crosshead velocities of 0.02 millimeters per second. Samples required 5 to 10 minutes for the maximum contact force to occur. In each case, the time force curve was smooth until it was reached. Afterwards, the force decreased somewhat erratically and was accompanied by popping noises indicating the integration of additional damage.

An initial drop height for each density was selected by trial-and-error. The initial heights were chosen so that a contact force of about 50% of the static test maximum contact force would be developed. From this initial setting, the drop weight height was increased until additional drop heights produced no higher contact force maximum. After this, the drop weight heights were decreased until a height was reached which produced no detectable impact damage.

Two techniques were used to determine the force producing incipient damage in these sandwich plates. Incipient damage was determined by: 1) decreasing the drop weight height until there was no visible asymmetry in the force-time curves and 2) noting at what level the impact force-time plot first deviated from a smooth curve. This point was characterized by substantial "ringing" in the accelerometer output. As it turns out, both methods produced results which were very similar. This is to be expected if the inertia of the plates is negligible in the impact event and if there are no significant time-dependent mechanics at work. A post-impact study of foam core structures has been reported by Caprino and Teti [5]; new theories of non-linear behavior mechanics have been proposed by Kuhhorn and Schoop [6], but our study did not extend past the energy producing maximum contact force since this constitutes failure of the outer face sheet.

The force-time histories for all twenty-three specimens of all three density core sandwich panels were numerically smoothed and displayed in an overlay as Figure 1. All impact tests on all twenty-three sandwich panels are included. These graphs are separated into three sections as a function of core densities and drop heights. For comparison, one overlaid graph of force-time histories for R-51 for the lowest, mid-level, and highest impact energies is also reproduced in *as recorded* format, Fig. 2.

Fig. 1: Force-time histories of impacted sandwich panels (smoothed data)

Fig. 2: Unsmoothed force-time histories for R-51 core panels

The fact that higher impact forces are developed in stiffer panels for a given drop height is easily seen in Fig. 3 where three specimens (numbers 4, 11, and 18) were subjected to [almost identical] drop heights of about 75 millimeters. The force change due to the foam cores is substantial even though all face sheets are identical. Note also the increased contact time and the equal impulse to all three specimens. The largest impact force developed in the R-71 highest density core panel specimen is 58% more than the force developed during impact with the R-31 specimen.

Fig. 3: The effect of stiffness on force-time history for a given drop height

Figs. 4 and 5 are overlays of tests on all twenty-three specimens. The maximum impact force is shown both as a function of drop height and core density. Least square generated curves are generated for the portion of the curves indicating a leveling-off at the high drop heights as a result of the inability of the specimen to sustain additional impact load.

For low drop heights, the R-51 and R-71 curves in Fig. 4 are linear as indicated by the dark lines. The R-31 curve is less linear in this range indicating the potential that some damage has already occurred. Impact duration in milliseconds is plotted vs. drop height for each of the three core density specimens. Fig. 5 shows data and a linear curve fit for each density foam. Even though there is scatter, the figure demonstrates that lower density cores contribute dramatically to the ability of the panels to decelerate the drop weight more slowly, thereby extending the drop height at which catastrophic failure occurs. As a practical measure, we attempted to compare the performance of sandwich panels to that of laminated panels of equivalent numbers of layers, panel dimensions, and fixture.

Fig. 4: Maximum impact force vs. drop height Fig. 5: Impact duration vs. drop height

Prior impact tests were conducted by the authors on 16, 32, and 48 ply laminated panels [7]. While these panels were made of quasi-isotropic layers of uniaxial laminates, the results attained on 16 ply panels parallels closely the current study. Fig. 6 shows a comparison of the threshold damage energy levels in panels in each study. Note that the energy required to produce incipient damage in the R-31 sandwich and the 16 ply laminates are virtually identical. What is remarkable is the energy required to produce threshold damage in sandwich panels. R-51 and R-71 density core sandwich composites with 9 ply plain weave graphite laminate face sheets are about as resistant to incipient damage as are laminated panels of 32 ply and 48 ply, respectively.

While sandwich panels are robust in absorbing energy without suffering incipient damage, they lack resistance to damage at higher energies. This is clearly shown in Fig. 7. In this case, the energy producing maximum force and damage of the front face sheet is plotted for each of the three density foam sandwich panels. Beside these data are plotted the equivalent energies producing backface spalling in 16, 32, and 48 ply laminated panels. Here there is substantial improvement in the laminated thicker panels.

Calculations were also made comparing the coefficients of D [bending stiffness] Matrix for the sandwich specimens with those of the laminated specimens of [7]. While bending stiffness coefficients for the laminated panels varied greatly, those of the sandwich panels were almost identical no matter which density core is used; they varied by less than 1%. In ongoing studies, deflection measurements were made on sandwich beams made of the same panels of this study. Such materials deflected up to four times the amount predicted by bending theory. This indicated that there is substantial shear deformation in low-density sandwich panels. This may also help explain the resistance of these panels to low energy impact.

Fig. 6: Energy required to produce incipient damage in both sandwich and laminated panels

Fig. 7: Damage tolerance of sandwich and laminated panels at peak energies

CONCLUSIONS

This work shows that damage in sandwich shells and laminated composite structural panels is substantially different. A major difference is the localization of damage in sandwich panels. In this case, the face sheets become more loaded in membrane rather than in bending. Another difference is the compliance of the core in sandwich panels as a factor in their damage resistance. While we did not present extended data about NDE techniques, we C-

SCANNED all tested panels. That information is currently being analyzed, however it has been difficult to determine the nature and degree of damage to sandwich panels through C-SCAN techniques.

Another interesting result is the substantial effect of core density on impact force. Higher impact forces were developed at a given drop height in panels made of stiffer cores even the classical laminate theory bending stiffness coefficients hardly changed. However, impact forces developed only until the material strength limit was reached no matter how much the impact energy was increased. At threshold damage levels, there was little difference in contact forces developed.

There was also no indication that the inertial of sandwich panels had an affect on the maximum force sustained at peak energy impact. Perhaps the most interesting finding was the ability of sandwich panels to perform exceedingly well in resisting initial damage. In fact, the higher density sandwich panels performed better than laminated panels of over 2.5 times their specific weight. On the other hand, if failure of a sandwich panel is defined as failure of the outer skin, then thin laminated panels perform about the same as sandwich panels while thick laminated panels perform substantially better.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

In closing, we wish to thank the NASA Center for Research Excellence for the support of Mr. Derke Hughes and for assisting with materials and travel expenses. We also wish to thank the Center for Composite Materials Research for the use of fabrication facilities and Wright Patterson Air Force Base for the use of structural testing and NDE facilities.

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